

Chelates of Praseodymium-, Neodymium-, Samarium-, Gadolinium-, Holmium-, Erbium-, Thulium- and Ytterbium(III) and some Symmetric 1,5-Diphenyl-3-cyanoformazans

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Potentiometric, conductimetric, ir, TG, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility studies have been carried out on the complexes of trivalent Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Ho, Er, Tm and Yb with some symmetric 1,5-diphenyl-3-cyanoformazans. The ionisation constants of the ligands and the formation constants of their metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically in solution. Complexation has also been studied by a conductimetric titration method.

Formazans serve as analytical reagents¹, the most famous one is known as zincon used as indicator for Zn, dye-stuffs² and also play a role in many biological³ and industrial processes. Since early studies, the field of coordination chemistry of formazans has received little attention particularly with the lanthanides⁴. They are capable of forming chelates with a number of metal ions⁵. The formation constants of some of the complexes were determined potentiometrically⁶. The chelates of lanthanum with some sym. 1,5-diphenyl-3-cyanoformazans [SDPCF] were studied applying different spectrometric and electrometric methods⁷.

The present investigation deals with the preparation and characterisation of the sym. 1,5-diphenyl-formazan chelates with the titled ions. The chelates were characterised using potentiometric, conductime-

tric, spectrophotometric, thermal and magnetic studies. The formazans under study were **1a-d**.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves, the \bar{n} values extend to 2.0 for all complexes, hence 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes are formed except for Er-with **1a**, 1 : 1 species is detected only. The results in Table 1 that the values of pK_{N-II} follow the order **1d** > **1b** > **1a** > **1c**. This may be explained by the electronegativities of the halogen atoms which exert strong inductive effect ($-I$ effect). In case of **1b**, the methyl group has the expected effect of lowering the acidity ($pK = 9.87$), whereas **1c** ($pK = 8.35$) manifests the withdrawal effect of the Cl group. For the *o*-COOH derivative (**1d**), the pK_{COOH} values are 3.90 and 5.56 in 50% alcohol, and 4.70 and 6.93 in 70% dioxane-water medium. The resulting carboxylate ions (electron-repelling) render difficult the release of proton from NH group.

Correlation between the $\log K_1$ and $\log \beta_2$ values of the lanthanide complexes as a function of atomic number, $1/r$ and EN (electronegativity) of the lanthanide metal ions (Fig. 1), exhibits the trend commonly found in many lanthanide complexes⁸. For the same ligand the formation constant increases till neodymium where it reaches a maximum and falls to sa-

a; X=H

b; X = *p*-CH₃

c; X=*p*-Cl

d; X = *o*-COOH

TABLE I-IONISATION CONSTANTS OF THE FORMAZANS (1a-d) AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF THEIR COMPLEXES

Metal	1a*			1b*			1c*			1d*			1d**		
	pK _{NH} = 9.33			pK _{NH} = 9.87			pK _{NH} = 8.35			pK _{NH} = 12.40, pK _{COOH} = 4.70 and 6.93			pK _{NH} = 11.76, pK _{COOH} = 3.9 and 5.56		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
Pr	7.03	6.98	14.01 (±0.04)	7.45	7.22	14.67 (±0.04)	5.98	5.87	11.85 (±0.1)	9.06	8.62	17.68 (±0.09)	10.08	9.07	19.15 (±0.08)
Nd	7.05	6.96	14.01 (±0.05)	7.70	7.56	15.26 (±0.08)	7.32	6.11	13.43 (±0.09)	12.02	8.98	21.00 (±0.07)	11.28	9.24	20.52 (±0.07)
Sm	-	-	-	8.30	7.80	16.10 (±0.06)	5.98	5.93	11.91 (±0.08)	9.15	8.78	17.93 (±0.09)	10.74	8.99	19.73 (±0.03)
Gd	7.06	6.99	14.05 (±0.04)	7.82	7.61	15.43 (±0.06)	6.17	6.03	12.20 (±0.07)	12.13	9.13	21.26 (±0.08)	11.15	8.94	20.09 (±0.06)
Ho	7.32	7.07	14.39 (±0.08)	8.40	7.76	16.16 (±0.09)	7.96	6.32	14.28 (±0.08)	11.90	8.99	20.89 (±0.09)	11.18	9.54	20.72 (±0.03)
Er	-	-	-	8.58	7.72	16.30 (±0.06)	7.72	6.38	14.10 (±0.07)	12.27	9.12	21.39 (±0.01)	11.03	9.32	20.35 (±0.05)
Tm	7.33	6.85	14.18 (±0.03)	8.95	7.85	16.80 (±0.09)	6.39	6.26	12.65 (±0.07)	11.06	8.89	19.95 (±0.07)	11.86	9.69	21.55 (±0.1)
Yb	9.64	7.48	17.12 (±0.09)	9.85	8.64	18.49 (±0.03)	8.95	8.82	17.77 (±0.08)	12.66	9.91	22.57 (±0.05)	12.00	10.73	22.73 (±0.07)

*In 70% dioxane-water mixture.

**In 50% ethanol-water-mixture.

Value in parenthesis is standard deviation (SD).

marium or gadolinium, and then increases again through the heavier lanthanides. The plots of Z^2/r of lanthanides vs log K_1 and log β_2 values (Born-Land relation) (Fig. 2) do not exhibit any linearity. This can be interpreted in term of the assumption that ionic character of metal-ligand on which the linearity is based, is totally not valid. The other probable causes are (i) coordination number of metal ion being greater than six and (ii) steric effects.

Budesinsky and Svecova⁹ justified the high stability of some complexes of cyanofornazan with transition metals as the combined action of coordination stability of individual metal ions, the M → L π-bonding and the chelate cage effects.

Conductimetric titration and molar conductance :
The results indicate that the conductance is increased with lowering the molar ratio [L]/[M], i.e. increase of M³⁺, as a result of releasing equivalent amount of

highly conducting H⁺ ions according to the increase of M³⁺. This may lead to the formation of 1 : 2 M : L species,

After complete conversion of formazan (HL) to the 1 : 2 species, the increase in conductance as a result of addition of Ln(ClO₄)₃ may be associated by formation of a new 1 : 1 species,

Titration curves of all ligands with all metal ions under investigation exhibit two intersections at 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complex species.

Molar conductivities of the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes Ln^{III}-1a are in the range 19.5–23.4 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹. The low values may be attributed to the coordination of perchlorate ions rather than ionic associa-

Fig 1 Relation between $\log K_1$ and $\log \beta_2$ of lanthanide complexes with formazans (**1a-d**) in 70% dioxane water mixture and atomic number (***1d** in 50% ethanol-water mixture)

tion of the lanthanide(III) cations during complex formation

Infrared spectra : The solid lanthanide chelates with **1a** were subjected to elemental analysis (Table 2). A comparison of the IR bands of the ligands¹⁰ and the results obtained from group theory treatment and normal coordinate analysis for **1a**¹¹ with their lanthanide chelates indicates that the NH group is still observed in the spectra of the chelates but it is shifted to higher or lower frequency (20 cm^{-1}). This offers a proof that the NH proton is not removed in the course of formation of the solid complexes (**1a** : $\nu_{\text{N-H}} 3218\text{ cm}^{-1}$) upon chelation, the $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching band (2225 cm^{-1}) is present in all complexes. The $\text{N}=\text{N}$ band is shifted to lower values in the chelates as a result of coordination with the metal ion (**1a** : $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}} 1445\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The coordination of perchlorate ion manifests itself by the

Fig 2 Relation between $\log K_1$ and $\log \beta_2$ of lanthanide complexes with formazans (**1a-d**) in 70% dioxane water mixture and the ionisation potential Z^2/r (***1d** in 50% ethanol-water mixture)

presence of bands at 1080 cm^{-1} and 625 cm^{-1} (Ref.12) The broad band at $3660\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (OH) confirms the participation of alcohol (solvent) molecules in the coordination sphere of the metal ion. On the other hand, some complexes display this band around 3400 cm^{-1} , which may be attributed to ν_{OH} of water. The complexes show new bands at 570 and 450 cm^{-1} attributed to $(\text{Ln} \leftarrow \text{N})$ and $(\text{Ln} \leftarrow \text{O})$ ¹³ respectively, which may be due to the formation of coordinate bond between the donor atom and central metal ion. This was supported by high electron density on these atoms of the ligand from the MO-PPP calculations¹⁰

Thermogravimetric analysis : The thermograms of the Nd and Pr complexes may be discussed as representatives. For Nd^{III} -**1a** complex, the first stage of decomposition in the range $85\text{--}140^\circ$ represents a loss of

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS DATA OF LANTHANIDE TRIVALENT COMPLEXES WITH FORMAZAN **1a**

Compd.	Formula	M L	Analysis % : Found/ (Calcd.)			
			C	H	Cl	M
Pr ^{III} - 1a	[Pr (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅).3ClO ₄ ·(C ₂ H ₅ OH) ₆]	1 : 1	32.60 (32.36)	4.90 4.90	11.30 11.02	15.10 14.60)
	[Pr(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅) ₂ .2OH ⁻ .ClO ₄ ⁻ .2H ₂ O]	1 : 2	41.50 (41.57)	3.60 3.49	4.50 4.39	17.80 17.42)
Nd ^{III} - 1a	[Nd(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅).3OH ⁻ .5H ₂ O]	1 : 1	31.60 (31.46)	4.60 4.53	— —	26.70 26.98)
	[Nd(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅) ₂ .ClO ₄ ⁻ .2OH ⁻ ·(C ₂ H ₅ OH) ₂]	1 : 2	45.30 (45.01)	4.90 5.03	3.60 3.69	15.30 15.02)
Sm ^{III} - 1a	[Sm(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅).2OH ⁻ .ClO ₄ ⁻ ·(C ₂ H ₅ OH) ₂]	1 : 1	34.30 (34.57)	4.00 4.03	5.40 5.68	23.80 24.05)
	[Sm(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅) ₂ .2OH ⁻ .ClO ₄ ⁻ ·H ₂ O·(C ₂ H ₅ OH) ₃]	1 : 2	43.40 (43.50)	4.60 4.70	3.80 3.78	15.80 16.02)
Gd ^{III} - 1a	[Gd(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅).2OH ⁻ .ClO ₄ ⁻ ·(C ₂ H ₅ OH) ₂]	1 : 1	34.20 (34.19)	3.80 3.99	5.50 5.01	25.20 24.88)
	[Gd(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅) ₂ .2OH ⁻ .ClO ₄ ⁻ ·5H ₂ O]	1 : 2	37.90 (38.25)	3.80 3.89	3.80 4.04	17.60 17.88)
Ho ^{III} - 1a	[Ho(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅).3ClO ₄ ⁻ ·(C ₂ H ₅ OH) ₆]	1 : 1	31.60 (31.57)	4.90 4.79	10.00 10.77	17.60 16.68)
	[Ho(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅) ₂ .2OH ⁻ .ClO ₄ ⁻ ·5H ₂ O]	1 : 2	37.80 (37.91)	4.00 3.86	4.20 4.10	18.10 18.59)
Er ^{III} - 1a	[Er(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅).3OH ⁻ ·(C ₂ H ₅ OH) ₄]	1 : 1	40.80 (40.54)	5.70 5.88	— —	26.10 25.66)
	[Er(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅) ₂ .3OH ⁻ ·(C ₂ H ₅ OH) ₄]	1 : 2	48.20 (47.98)	5.30 5.48	— —	18.10 18.56)
Yb ^{III} - 1a	[Yb(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅).2OH ⁻ .ClO ₄ ⁻ ·H ₂ O·C ₂ H ₅ OH]	1 : 1	31.00 (31.00)	3.70 3.41	5.90 5.73	28.10 27.92)
	[Yb(C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₅) ₂ .3OH ⁻ ·H ₂ O]	1 : 2	46.00 (45.40)	3.60 3.67	— —	23.10 23.37)

one molecule of water of hydration. At 140–185° about 3.48% mass-loss refers to one coordinated water molecule. Heating at 185–210° results the loss of three coordinated water molecules. In case of Pr^{III}-**1a**, the loss at 40–190° is attributed to one molecule of water of hydration together with one coordinated water molecule. Nd^{III}-**1a** complex shows an inflection at 325–450° attributed to the unstable intermediate formed. The final stage at 450–650° involves the conversion of such intermediates to the stoichiometric oxide Nd₂O₃, while for 1 : 2 Pr^{III}-**1a** the non-stoichiometric oxide Pr₆O₁₁ is formed as the final product.

Magnetic susceptibility : The magnetic susceptibility was measured using Faraday's method¹⁴, for the

ligand **1a** and its complexes. The ligand exhibited a diamagnetic susceptibility with a typical value of -1.363×10^{-3} emu/g. The effective magnetic moment (μ) per formula unit was calculated using the expression : $\mu = 2.84 (\chi_m T)^{0.5}$, where χ_m is the molar susceptibility (including the magnetic correction). The magnetic moment of the tripositive lanthanide metal ions is calculated as $\mu_{cal} = g[J(J + 1)^{0.5}]$, where J is the total angular momentum and g the gyromagnetic ratio, and μ_{ex} the experimental value of the effective magnetic moment of the lanthanide ion, found in literature¹⁵. The present complexes are found paramagnetic except that of Sm^{III} which is diamagnetic. The values of μ are found less than the corresponding μ_{cal} and μ_{ex} by typical values within the range 0.9–3.3 B.M.

This discrepancy is nearly in the order of the spin-only magnetic moment of 1 or 2 electrons, i.e. 1.73 or 3.46 B.M. respectively¹⁶.

The paramagnetic range of plots of the temperature dependence of the reciprocal susceptibility for $\text{Ho}^{\text{III}}\text{-1a}$ (1 : 1) and $\text{Er}^{\text{III}}\text{-1a}$ (1 : 2) complexes in the temperature range 94–3000 K, are found to obey Curie-Weiss law,

$$\chi = C / (T - \theta_p)$$

where C is the Curie's constant and θ_p the Curie paramagnetic temperature. The obtained values of θ_p were 6 and 39 K respectively for $\text{Ho}^{\text{III}}\text{-1a}$ and $\text{Er}^{\text{III}}\text{-1a}$ complexes. The positive values of θ_p ruled out the predominance of antiferromagnetic interaction.

In the light of the above findings, the structure of (1 : 1) $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}}\text{-1a}$ and (1 : 2) $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-1a}$ chelates may be represented as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. (A) $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}}\text{-1a}$ (1 : 1). (B) $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-1a}$ (1 : 2)

Accordingly the lanthanide metal ion is expected to have a coordination number 9 and 8 for the 1 : 1 $\text{Nd}^{\text{III}}\text{-1a}$ and 1 : 2 $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}}\text{-1a}$ complexes respectively.

Experimental

The stability constants of trivalent Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd,

Ho, Er, Tm and Yb ions with the ligands (SDPCF) in 70% dioxane-water mixture at 25° and 0.1 M ionic strength were determined by the reported technique¹⁷. For *o*-COOH derivative, the stability constants of its lanthanide complexes were also investigated in 50% ethanol-water mixture since permanent turbidity occurred in case of other formazans. Ir, TG, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility measurements of the chelates were performed. All the chemicals used in this study were of pure B.D.H. grade. The formazans (**1a-d**) were prepared by the reported method⁷.

Stock ethanolic formazan solutions (10^{-3} M) were prepared. Lanthanide perchlorate solutions (10^{-3} M) were prepared¹⁸ and standardised¹⁹. Three mixtures were prepared²⁰ and titrated against standard NaOH solution using a Seibold G 103 pH meter at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The titrations were performed twice to test the reproducibility. The ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$, was kept constant by adding appropriate amount of 1 M NaClO_4 . The pH meter reading was corrected for different solvents²¹.

The average number of protons (\bar{n}_A) associated with the ligand at various pH values, the average number of ligand (\bar{n}) attached to a metal ion and the free ligand exponent (pL) were calculated¹⁷. The successive stability constants were evaluated by correction term method and the best set of stability constants was obtained from experimental values \bar{n} and $[L]$ and are restricted to systems for which $N = 2$ (Ref. 22). Conductimetric titrations of 50 ml 4×10^{-5} M of the formazans (**1a-d**) with 10^{-3} M $\text{Ln}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ solutions were carried out using a D812 LBR conductivity meter at a frequency of 3 KHz.

The solid complexes were prepared and studied as described elsewhere⁷. The magnetic studies were made at 300 K using Faraday's method¹⁴.

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